

**COMPLIANCE WITH RESPONSIBILITY AND WORK REGIMES OF
DRIVERS IN LEGAL REGULATORY DOCUMENTS DUE TO ACCIDENTS IN
THE TRANSPORTATION OF INTERNATIONAL GOODS BY TRUCKS**

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Abstract

This article contains reminders for companies and drivers that carry out transportation in international trucks, examples of legal documents, compliance with these, and tasks that must be performed in connection with the inclusion of the Republic of Uzbekistan in international transportation agreements.

Keywords: Freight speed, high value cargo, European agreement, AETR agreement, technical support.

Introduction

This article contains reminders for companies and drivers that carry out transportation in international trucks, examples of legal documents, compliance with these, and tasks that must be performed in connection with the inclusion of the Republic of Uzbekistan in international transportation agreements. Uzbekistan is located in the center of Central Asia from the point of view of location and is of great importance in the world transport corridor. Therefore, the use of this opportunity can be seen from the decisions made by our government, the international convention that is expected to be joined, and the acceleration of our joining the economic blocs. Maximum use of transit potential will provide new professions and income for Uzbekistan. It is necessary to provide transit routes located in our republic with all facilities for carriers engaged in transit and international cargo transportation. Because only and only economic effect is achieved with this.

Results and discussion

The speed and quality of cargo transportation are always important for the successful operation of companies, as well as for the dynamic development of production and trade relations in cities and countries.

As the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan is growing steadily in the coming years, the market of motor transport services is also developing.

The average annual growth rate of the truck fleet is 2...3%, while the material base of motor vehicles has increased 3...4 times over the last 6 years. This corresponds to the economic development of the republic. Road transport is the main mode of transport, carrying out more than 90% of domestic and international cargo transportation.

There is no other type of transport comparable to automobile transport in the transportation of valuable goods over short and medium distances, in the transportation of retail and industrial goods, in the logistics system, and in providing services to small businesses.

In the process of international integration, the importance of road transport in foreign trade has increased significantly. In the next 6 years, the volume of these cargoes increased 12 times [1].

Based on these, it is necessary to take into account that it is the duty of the carrier to deliver the cargo to its destination on time and without compromising its quality. The carrier must monitor the compliance of the driver attached to the vehicle with work modes and rest periods.

Let's get acquainted with the adopted normative legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the responsibilities in them.

Decision No. N340 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 22, 2011 "On the introduction of digital control devices in vehicles carrying international goods" In order to fulfill the obligations of the Republic of Uzbekistan related to the participation in the European agreement on the work of crews of international cargo-carrying vehicles in the city, the Cabinet DECIDES:

In 1998, the Republic of Uzbekistan joined the European agreement on the work of crews of international cargo vehicles;

In accordance with the requirements of the European agreement, after June 16, 2010, the countries that are participants of the European agreement should be provided with digital control devices for international cargo vehicles.

2. The Ministry of Transport of the Republic of Uzbekistan should be designated as the competent body for fulfilling the obligations of the Republic of Uzbekistan related to the participation of Uzbekistan in the European agreement.

3. Ministry of Transport of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

In accordance with the requirements of the European agreement, the regulation on digital control device cards used to control the work and rest modes of drivers in international cargo transportation by car, as well as the instruction on the use of digital control devices should be developed within one month and in the prescribed manner. confirmation;

that in accordance with the requirements of the European agreement, the gradual introduction of digital control devices and their use will be coordinated;

It is said to ensure the implementation of measures for the introduction of a system of digital control devices in motor vehicles of the Republic of Uzbekistan that carry out international cargo transportation by car, and if the distance of car cargo transportation is 400 km or more, or if the cargo takes 9 hours or more it is said that two drivers must be attached to that vehicle if it is within the delivery distance. Drivers are required to rest for 15 minutes every 1.5 hours or 45 minutes every 4.5 hours [2].

AETR Agreement Schedule of Rules Defining Driving Periods, Breaks and Rest Periods (2010)

Table-1

Rules and norms	Excerpt from AETR
Maximum time of uninterrupted management	4.5 hours (Article 7 Clause 1)
Maximum control time during the day	9 hours, 10 hours twice a week
Maximum management time for a week/fortnight	56 hours (Article 6, Clause 2)/for two consecutive weeks 90th hour (Article 6 Clause 3)
Maximum number of driving cycles before weekly rest	A weekly rest period must begin no later than the end of the six 24-hour period beginning after the end of the previous rest period.
Minimum break time	45 minutes, it is allowed to divide the rest time into two intervals (the first is 15 minutes, the second is 30 minutes, continue no later than the end of the four-hour control). The purpose of this article is not used for driving and waiting time in a moving vehicle, ferry or train is not considered as another work defined in article 1 of this Agreement and must meet the break
Daily rest time	11 hours, Between the two-week holidays, permission is granted for 9 hours up to three times a week (paragraph 5 of Article 8) During 12 hours, the first three times, the second

	time interval is not less than 9 hours
Weekly time off	For one driver (Driver brigade) - 45 hours, for a car - once every two weeks no more than 24 hours If the weekly rest period is reduced, the driver must be compensated no later than the end of the third week
A crew of two or more drivers	After 30 hours of work, every driver must rest for at least 9 hours continuously
NOTE	In cases of daily and reduced weekly rest, it is allowed to use the car salon for rest only in the parking lot It is allowed to reduce the daily rest time without requiring compensation Any rest period used to compensate for reduced weekly rest periods must be added to another rest period of at least 9 hours (Article 8, Clause 8). Crew members must be present at all times and present log sheets for verification, times must cover the current day and the previous 28 calendar days; the driver's card, if any, must be printed with manual entries for the current and previous 28 calendar days as required by this Agreement. If the driver is unable to provide the above documents, he must provide the activity confirmation form for this period. The form of the form is given in Annex 3 of AETR.

According to the above table (Table 1) of the AETR, the principle of ex-territoriality was introduced, i.e.: The contracting party gives its competent authorities the right to apply sanctions:

for a driver's violation of this Agreement that has been identified in that territory and for which no sanction has yet been imposed, even if the violation was committed in another Contracting Party or in a non-Contracting State.

An enterprise that has been found to have violated this Agreement in its territory and no sanctions have yet been applied against it, even if the violation was committed in the territory of another Contracting Party or a non-Contracting State.

Article 9 of the AETR

Withdrawals

In order not to endanger road safety and to reach a convenient parking place, the driver may depart from the provisions of this Agreement to the extent necessary to ensure the safety of persons walking in the vehicle, the vehicle or the cargo on it. The driver must indicate the nature and reason for the departure from these provisions in the registration sheet or on the printout of the control device or in his statement no later than at the time of arrival at a suitable parking place [3].

The duration of continuous control by one driver is no more than 4.5 hours.

Increase daytime management time:

The duration of the daily management time can be increased to 10 hours only 2 times during any one week. The countdown time for the duration of the week starts at 0:00 on Monday and ends at 24:00 on Sunday, regardless of which day of the week the driver started driving the vehicle.

Daily duration of management, no more than nine hours. It can be increased to a maximum of 10 hours no more than twice during the week.

Comment: The driver can independently determine the duration of driving and bridge breaks. considering the restriction on continuous driving. For example

Duration of daily management by a crew of two drivers

For the purposes of this article, waiting time and time not used for driving and spent in a moving vehicle, on a ferry or a train are not considered as "other work" defined in article 1 (e) of this Agreement, and should be qualified as a "break".

In order to avoid additional questions from regulatory authorities, it is recommended to do it.

For a crew of 2 drivers, the time not used to control the PBX (traffic jam, loading and unloading, border crossing) reduces the allowed maximum control time.

Devices that record the time of work and rest of drivers

Electronic (analog) tachograph M. The latest generation of CCU 3283 1324

Digital tachographs allowed to MAP

Types of digital tachographs with AETR type approval

VDO

ACTIA

STONERIDGE

EFAS

Digital tachographs manufactured in Russia, for example: Atol, Mercury, Casbi, Barcode, etc. are not yet recognized in the EU countries, as they do not have a certificate "Approval of types of control devices AETR-AETR".

Digital tachographs that have certificates and are allowed to be used in the MAП ECTP-AETR: VDO, STONERIDGE, EFAS and ACTIA.

Rules of one minute (convenience of passing traffic jams)

Modern digital tachographs (CCU- Digital Control Device) have a number of advantages over analog tachographs. One of the most important advantages of the CCU is the one-minute rule.

This rule represents a period of time in which the movement of the PBX lasting no more than 29 seconds is not taken into account (does not add up to the total control time).

Tachographs of the EFAS brand have advantages over other tachographs in recording control time. EFAS tachographs do not register the driving time while driving if the speed of the PBX does not exceed 8-10 km/h.

Article 16 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Road Traffic Safety" (19.08.1999 N818-I) provides for legal entities and individual entrepreneurs whose activities are related to the use of vehicles. requirements are listed, and clauses 1 and 2 of these requirements are described as follows:

- organizing the work of vehicle drivers in accordance with the requirements for road safety;
- it is said to observe the regime of work and rest of the drivers established by the legislation.

Article 11 of this law states at the beginning of letter 2.

-Damage caused due to road traffic accidents caused by the non-fulfillment of the obligations imposed on the road management bodies, due to the road conditions, should be compensated by these bodies in accordance with the procedure established by the law.

Article 38 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Guarantees of Freedom of Business Activity" (25.05.2000 No. 69-II) states that the damage caused to the subject of business activity shall be borne by the person who caused the damage in full, including , must be compensated by adding lost profits. It is said that a person who is not the causer of damage can be charged with the obligation to compensate for the damage by law.

This is stated at the beginning of letter 9 of section III, paragraph 26 of Annex 1 to the Cabinet of Ministers Resolution No. 342 of December 26, 2011, "On the provision and organization of safety in the region of highways in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan". , in which vehicle repair and lubrication, refueling, loading, unloading, loading and securing of loads to other equipment, cleaning and washing are prohibited on highways and their safety zones.

As can be seen from these normative legal documents, when the vehicle moves on the roads, it is necessary to move the cargo to the destination within the agreed terms of the contract, without causing damage and observing the safety of traffic to other road users [4].

Research part

Drivers of vehicles need to stop outside roads that pose a threat to traffic safety in order to stop for rest or perform technical maintenance.

Clause 33 of this decision on the equipment of roads of international importance in our republic prohibits the construction of buildings at a close distance on both sides of roads of category I and II.

On one side of highways, in the following cases, on the basis of approved urban planning documents, construction of buildings on agricultural land on the basis of agriculture, objects in accordance with the procedure established by government decisions: from the edge of the carriageway:

- in open places - 200 meters away;
- it can be placed in residential areas, on the side of highways where the boundaries of settlements meet - at a distance of 100 meters.

Unfortunately, we cannot say that there are constructions on our roads based on legal documents.

Taking this into account, a safe zone should be created on transit roads for international freight vehicles in our country.

Figure 1. Map of the A373 motorway and safe parking areas for lorries.

There are 99 transit routes in our republic, most of them cross the A373 highway. The A373 highway is 399 km long and consists of flat roads, mountain roads, and mountain roads. We studied the area of A373 highway 90 km from Andijan region

and determined on our map that a safe parking place is needed for 340 km of A373 highway. Because the traffic flow here is given in the table below.

Table-2

Histogram 2. Daily traffic flow on 340 kilometers of the A373 highway.

As can be seen from this table, the traffic flow is between 1492 and 1915 per hour. The number of foreign trucks goes from 1 to 6 per hour, and trucks go from 85 to 128. The capacity of the road, if trucks are parked on the side of the road, will reduce the technical speed of all other vehicles, and will create traffic jams. In order to avoid traffic jams and road traffic accidents, we present below the map of the safe parking place for trucks for this kilometer. In this drawing, we have designed a safe parking area with lines inclined at 30° to the road, because after the road base there is a field where the truck can easily park and continue on its way. for. There are additional toilets, car service, scales, rest rooms for crews. We assumed that the safe parking area is 40 m² per car and the number of trucks is 10 units at most. The reason is that it is intended for the intermediate rest periods of drivers under the AETR contract [5].

Figure 3. Safe parking on a 30° slope to the road.

If we organize such stops along the transit routes of our republic, we will prevent traffic accidents, have a positive effect on the environment, keep the technical speed at the same level, and at the bottom of all this, we will achieve economic efficiency.

Our country is on the verge of becoming a member of international economic blocs, so it is time to adapt our transport potential and road infrastructure to global requirements.

Conclusion

The export potential of our republic can be increased several times with agricultural products and mineral fertilizers. For this purpose, the place of transport logistics is incomparable for us. If we organize safe stops on transit routes for national transport companies and international transport drivers of our republic, we will prevent all kinds of unfortunate incidents, material losses, and intergovernmental responsibilities in the future. The expected transit in the near future will also create grounds for increasing the number of passing traffic flows. In addition, we will work according to the AETR contract. All this is for human dignity.

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